

Proposal for a Collaborative Data Infrastructure for Control of DEMs

Ariza-López F.J., Ureña-Cámara
M.A.

Dpto. Ingeniería Cartográfica,
Geodésica y Fotogrametría.
Universidad de Jaén
Jaén, España

fjariza@ujaen.es, maurena@ujaen.es

Reinoso-Gordo J.F.

Dpto. Expresión Gráfica
Arquitectónica y en la Ingeniería
Universidad de Granada
Granada, España
jreinoso@ugr.es

Nero M.A.

Centro de Geociências
Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais
Belo Horizonte, Brasila
marcelo.nero@gmail.com

Abstract— Global digital elevation models are well suited for many applications and therefore their quality needs to be evaluated. However, the evaluation of this type of data is expensive and efforts are often repeated. In addition, in certain global applications, the possibility of accessing local control data is missing. This paper proposes the design of a collaborative data infrastructure for the control of digital elevation models. Specifically, the data model related to the control part is established and, in addition, it must support the collaborative web application. The data may be of point type (e.g. points surveyed by Global Navigation Satellite Systems), transect (e.g. altimetric profiles or paths), or surface (e.g. a high density and accuracy patches). It is a flexible design that incorporates metadata for subsequent filtering. Along with the spatial and temporal aspects of the data, metadata attributes related to accuracy, instrumentation, operator, etc., are also included. All of these attributes must allow content to be properly filtered to provide adequate reference data for Digital Terrain Models (DTM) and Digital Surface Models (DSM) assessments.

most critical aspect is usually having adequate reference data to be able to carry out the subsequent statistical analysis (e.g. an estimate of error), with sufficient statistical representativeness.

Traditionally, in the case of geodetic and topographic surveys, the existing infrastructures, both in its physical part (monumentalized), and in its documental part, allowed the development of new and interoperable surveys with those already existing. Our idea is to offer an infrastructure that minimizes the cost of evaluating the accuracy of new GDEMs. This infrastructure will allow the reuse of existing evaluation work. In addition, it will allow collaboration between users and producers.

The objective of this document is to present the design of the proposed data infrastructure, justify some of the decisions made and explain its synergy between this infrastructure and the DEMIX project (Digital Elevation Model Intercomparison eXperiment).

I. INTRODUCTION)

Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are a typology of geospatial data product included in the Global Fundamental Geospatial Data Themes defined by the United Nations Committee of Experts for Global Geospatial Information Management [1]. DEMs have a significant role on numerous sustainable development goals of the United Nations (e.g. the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 6th, 7th, 11th, 13th, 14th and 15th goals). For this reason, the quality of the DEM data is relevant and its control is required, especially at this time in which numerous applications are being developed on the so-called Global Digital Elevation Models (GDEM). Quality in DEM is mostly understood as an assessment of positional accuracy [2, 3], that is vertical accuracy; and the

II. GDEM ASSESSMENT, CONTROL INFRASTRUCTURES AND THE DEMIX PROJECT

A. Control infrastructures

Geospatial data refers to a changing reality such as the real world. For this reason, there is a need to update the geospatial data of a specific area, more frequently when greater dynamics of that area (e.g., new urban developments, etc.). So that, it is usual for the same area to have products from different times, depending on the update strategies adopted by the data producers.

Some elements of geospatial data quality (in the sense of ISO 19157) [4] require that quality be assessed against a reference,

usually ground-truthing data. An adequate reference requires independence with respect to the data to be evaluated and also greater accuracy. This makes generating the references costly and therefore it is usual to work with processes based on statistical sampling. It is also common to try to reuse reference data from previous evaluation processes, as long as they remain valid. This is the main justification for a control data infrastructure. There are several examples of geospatial data producers that have created their own control infrastructures (e.g. the Lucas facility by the European Environment Agency) [5]. In the case of GDEM, Becek et al. 2022 [6] proposed the Global Elevation Data Testing Facility (GEDTF). It is defined as “a database of anthropogenic and natural features found around the world that are flat (or nearly flat) and large (longer than 500m and wider than 15m)” (<https://zasobynauki.pl/zasoby/global-elevation-data-testing-facility-gedtf,49859/>)

B. GDEM assessment

GDEMs are commonly used for global studies by international user communities or organization. GDEMs are a type of data widely used today due to the interest in the analysis of various processes on a global scale (e.g. climate change). As indicated by [7] there is a need for a high-accuracy, open-access GDEMs. For this reason, there exists a great interest in knowing the quality of the various offered products, many of them available under a free and open data policy (e.g., NASADEM 1”, SRTM 3” and 1”, ASTER-GDEM v3, AW3D30 1”, TanDEM-X90, Copernicus DEM 3” and 1”, MERIT). Some analyses are:

- Iwao et al. [8] compared elevation values of GTOPO30 and SRTM 30 arc second datasets globally at degree confluences by means of GNSS data.
- Xinchuan et al. [9] used five GDEMs (ASTER GDEM2, SRTM V4.1, GMTED2010, EarthEnv-DEM90, and GTOPO30) and compare them with ICESat/GLA14 data to assess the accuracy.
- Acharya et al. [10] develop a comparison of the AW3D30 (Advanced Land Observing Satellite World 3D 30m) and SRTM30 (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission Global 30m) using as reference a 30m resampled LiDAR DEM.
- Uemaa et al. [11] examined the accuracy of six freely available global DEMs (ASTER, AW3D30, MERIT, TanDEM-X, SRTM, and NASADEM) in four geographic regions with different topographic and land use conditions. They used local high-precision LiDAR and Pleiades-1A data as reference.
- Geoffroy and Guth [12] used high-resolution ICESat-2 point clouds to evaluate several GDEM (SRTM (V3), ASTER GDEM and ALOS World 3D AW3D30).

and many others.

A general conclusion of these works is the lack of a common analysis method, and the lack of a common reference data set for the GDEM quality assessments.

C. The DEMIX project and the control infrastructures

The DEMIX project focuses on being able to suggest the best GDEM for a use case in a given area, and for this, reference data on a global scale is required. To date, the DEMIX project has focused on the development of definitions, use cases, the proposal of functional quality measures and the development of a statistical method for decision making based on qualitative and quantitative judgments.

According to [13], developing a test protocol and several comparison criteria is proposed to compare different GDEMs. In the comparison they will use a number of independent test sites (tiles), where in each of them must exist a reference dataset, deemed to be of higher accuracy. The reference data of a tile has an owner (“tile-owner”). It is desired to find a number of tiles, spread over the world that are representative of varying landforms and landscapes. The idea is to declare that a particular global DEM is better than the others, there is no reason to expect that it will be better in all the tiles.

Based on the evaluations for each GDEM and the typologies of the tiles, DEMIX proposes to create a web tool that guides the users of the GDEM so that they themselves choose the product (e.g., STRM, ASTER, TanDEM-X90, etc.) that performs best in areas equivalent to those of their interest.

We consider that there is a high degree of synergy and complementarity between the DEMIX project and the proposal of a control infrastructure. Having a collaborative and global control infrastructure will make it possible to have control data on a global scale, such as the GDEMs. This will allow for more comprehensive assessments. In addition, it will allow researchers to access the same set of reference data, and this will allow more interoperable results between different evaluation analyses. Having control data on a global scale in an open infrastructure does not limit the possible measures to be applied, it is only necessary to include the appropriate types of reference data for each use case (for example, altimetric points for vertical accuracy control and a drainage network for an evaluation on this use case).

III. THE CONTROL DATA INFRASTRUCTURE FOR GDEMS

A. Control infrastructures

The control-data infrastructure for DEM is a facility developed under the following criteria:

- Data Openness. Legal and technical openness by means of open data licenses and non-proprietary formats and access.
- Open contribution and cooperation. The infrastructure is open to receiving contributions from any interested party, with the only restriction of accepting the opening of the data and the technical supervision of their contributions.
- Web application. It is a web-accessible application.

The goal of this infrastructure is to provide reference data sets (points, profiles, surfaces and other data types) that can be used to evaluate the quality of DTMs (digital terrain models) and DSMs (digital surface models) (see [12] for a definition on DTM and DSM). The basic elements constituting the infrastructure are a database that houses the reference data and all the relevant metadata around them (e.g. authorship, accuracy, dates, methods, etc.), and the Web application that offers the service and interfaces with administrators and users. To achieve this purpose, the following bases are required:

- Data with adequate characteristics to serve as a reference data in quality assessment processes.
- Metadata that allows knowing key aspects of the reference data and being able to filter them based on their characteristics and user needs.
- Web system for collaboration and consultation.
- A data model that allows managing data, metadata, collaborations and access.

Our vision about the use of the infrastructure is as follows: this infrastructure should allow the user to filter their content considering time (e.g., date range), space (e.g., introducing a geographic window), type of application (e.g., DTM or DSM), resolution of the data to be controlled (e.g., 1", 3", etc.), and any other criteria that is considered relevant for a quality assessment and that is present in the metadata.

The database that has been designed contains two branches of interest (Figure 1):

- The branch of the responsible party (red branch of Figure 1). This branch is intended to store data relevant to those users who provide the control data (control-data owners) (e.g. name, address, phone, etc.).
- The branch of the control data set (blue branch of Figure 1). This branch is intended to store the control data in a structured way and with its appropriate metadata.

The participation of an individual or organization is done by means of one or several control datasets (*Ctr_DataSet*). Each control dataset must contain at least one control entity (*Ctr_Entity*). The control entities can be of the type point (*Points*), profile (*Profiles*) or surface (*Surfaces*) (Figure 2). Finally, the coordinates of the control structures are stored as triplets of X, Y and Z values (*Coordinates*). The control data sets, the control entities, the points, profiles and coordinates, are

objects that have properties (e.g., minimum bounding box, date, accuracy, CRS, etc.), which allow the appropriate selection of the control data.

From the users' perspective, the main use cases considered are the following:

- Users (all): Register/deregister in the system.
- Users providing control data: Create control data sets, along with their metadata.
- Users providing control data: Upload control entities that are included in control data sets, along with their metadata.
- Data infrastructure users: Perform queries.
- Data infrastructure users: Download control data to perform their analysis.

Currently, the database for the infrastructure is in the final design phase. Tests are being carried out with the data corresponding to the geodetic network of Spain (points), road axes (3D profiles) and patches (surfaces) from surveys using laser techniques (aerial and terrestrial). It is now being tested in single user mode. The phase is scheduled to be completed by the end of Summer 2023. It is planned to develop a user management system with adequate capabilities (e.g. registration, log, etc.). It is scheduled to put the system into production at the end of 2023. All the development is done with open software tools and the database manager is PostGIS.

Figure 1. Database model schema, main object classes of the two branches: the responsible of the data (in red) and the data for the DEM control (in blue).

Figure 2. Example of control entities: geodetic monument, football pitch, parking zone, flat roof, pitched roof, airfield runway and a road

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The DEMIX project focuses on being able to suggest the best DEM for a use case in a given area, and for this, reference data on a global scale is required. To date, the DEMIX project has focused on the development of definitions, use cases, the proposal of functional quality measures, and the development of a statistical method for decision making based on qualitative and quantitative judgments.

With a global perspective, our proposed infrastructure allows hosting control elements of a very diverse nature in a structured and use-oriented manner. Thanks to the considered metadata, it will be possible to filter control elements appropriate to the accuracy and space-time requirements of the DEM (or DSM) data to be controlled. For all these reasons, our infrastructure allows hosting the control tiles considered in the DEMIX project.

The development of the infrastructure is mature but not closed, which allows some modifications to be included in the data model, such that they could be relevant for the DEMIX project. The infrastructure is currently in the testing phase regarding the design of the database and the web service component is starting. It is expected to be operational by the beginning of 2024.

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